

The Physical Vacuum as the “Immaterial Fluid” Medium: Fundamental Equations, Time Emergence, Light Speed Invariance, and Interference Invariance in the Michelson–Morley Experiment

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Abstract

Starting from the main known experimental evidence, we have already published articles in which we describe the structure of a superfluid medium that has the same behavior of the physical vacuum. We have called it Immaterial Fluid. In the present article we derive the fundamental equations characterizing the behavior of the elementary particles that constitute the Immaterial Fluid. We describe how time arises as an emergent property of the Immaterial Fluid. We demonstrate both physically and mathematically why, through the Immaterial Fluid, light always propagates at a constant speed. We therefore physically explain why, considering the presence of the Immaterial Fluid, still no interference variation is observed in the Michelson-Morley experiment. To further demonstrate the internal consistency of the model, this paper presents a formulation developed in both quantum and classical mathematical frameworks. In the previous articles, we have developed a mathematical model that describes the Immaterial Fluid as massless and Lorentz-invariant. We have explained how the gravitational field emerges from the Immaterial fluid, and how the generation of pairs occurs. From the Immaterial Fluid, we have also derived Maxwell equations, and have described how the wave propagates through the particles that make up the fluid. This provides a possible, clear explanation of what virtual particles are and how they arise.

Introduction

This article develops and clarifies concepts that we published in previous articles [1, 2, 3]. We built a model considering the physical vacuum as the “Immaterial Fluid” medium [1]. It is constituted by immaterial bosons, that we have called Immaterial Atoms, IAs [1]. We have already described structure and behavior of IAs [1, 2, 3], and we will summarize them in Methods. To demonstrate the internal consistency of the model, in addition to a covariant and quantum description [1], we developed a classical formalization [1, 2, 3], through which we physically describe the pair generation process. We believe that a description that is possible in multiple distinct

ways is technically more robust and deeper than one that is possible only in a way [1, 6, 7]. Both mathematical analyses, presented here as an initial level, can be further developed and deepened. Through the classical model, we obtained an equation, the Ultimate Equilibrium Equation, that physically describes pairs generation when two electromagnetic waves in vacuum collide head on with an energy $E=880\text{MeV}$, which is in the range of gamma rays [1, 2, 5]. The pairs generation mechanism described [1, 2] is only one among the possible conceivable options [1] considering the physical vacuum as the Immaterial Fluid. To show the coherence of the model, by adopting the same, unrealistic assumptions historically used in calculating the classical radius of the electron [26, 70], we have obtained the exact same value of the classical radius, but through a different procedure [1]. We also provided an energy balance of the pair generation process [2]. This mechanism, i.e. the transition from immaterial to real state [1, 2], is comparable to a kind of transition state of the Immaterial Fluid medium [1, 8, 9]. In the present article too, the conclusions we reach are obtained both through quantum and classical mathematical frameworks.

Starting from the spacetime represented by the Immaterial Fluid, we have furthermore developed another model that is consistent with the main known experimental observations. Through this model, we provide simple and clear interpretations and descriptions of neutrons and protons, of the confinement of quarks, of the strong interaction, how gluons are made, the transformation of down quark into up quark during β^- decay, the structure of the weak W^- boson, the three generations of leptons, and more [4]. It follows that all matter in the universe could be described as arising from a suitable combination of real electrons and positrons [4]. Baryogenesis will be presented in subsequent works. From the immaterial fluid derive other interpretations for phenomena whose underlying mechanism remains debated [1]. For example, dark matter, dark energy, entanglement, inflation, neutrinos, wave-particle duality, the two-slit experiment, and so on. These concepts will be presented as soon as they are completed.

Methods

We start from a physically contemplable situation in which, at the very least within certain energy values, the physical vacuum of a region of space-time is actually the Immaterial Fluid medium, made up of a discrete number of Immaterial Atom bosons, IAs [1, 2, 3]. It has the same behavior of the vacuum and, on a macroscopic scale, it can be considered continuous, homogeneous and isotropic [1]. Each IA is made up by the overlap of two immaterial, pure elementary electric leptonic charges [1] $e+$ and

e-. We call “immaterial” the state (different from real) in which the two leptons that make up an IA totally overlap each other or, due to the oscillation procured by a wave, partially overlap. In the latter case, they temporary partially separate and become partially distinguishable from each other [1]. When this happens, we have identified them as the known virtual particles that carry the waves [1]. Due to the IAs oscillation, they indeed continuously emerge and then annihilate [1, 15, 16]. We use the term “immaterial” to indicate that they may not possess a real (on-shell) mass and we can’t directly perceive them [1], as for virtual particles [15]. Immaterial and virtual particles are related, because, in our model, virtual particles emerge from IAs oscillation during wave transmission [1]. We use the term “immaterial” instead of “virtual” because we consider the immaterial particles as already existent in the Immaterial Fluid [1]. Instead, in conventional quantum field theory, virtual particles are not considered to standalone entities. Rather, they indicate temporary intermediate states in interactions and do not possess independent ontological status [128, 129, 130]. We consider the hypothetical situation of stable, unperturbed equilibrium [1], where no wave or fluctuation transit through them. In the reality, due at the very least to the background radiation or Higgs field fluctuations, this condition is never achievable [15, 16]. In this hypothetical state, the two immaterial leptons perfectly overlap, with coincident spin axis [1, 2]. The magnetic dipoles (Note A) of the overlapping leptons cancel each other out and their electric fields have opposite sign [1, 23], so they have zero fields and no mass [1, 2, 15]. We define “masking” the overlap of the two immaterial leptons [1, 2, 3]. Based on IAs behavior, we can think on a total or partial masking, corresponding to total or partial overlap of the immaterial leptonic charges [1, 2, 3]. We consider the situation in which spacetime is a three-dimensional network made up of IAs [1, 2, 3]. Each IA occupies a discrete position in the network [1]. Waves transit thorough each other adjacent IAs, that have alternated oriented spin $s=+1h$ and $s=-1h$ [1, 3]. The electromagnetic wave has to be considered as the propagation of IAs polarization from an IA to the adjacent one and so on [1, 3]. In analogy with other studies [23, 51, 102], the polarization of the IA is possible because they are made by the overlap of two leptons with opposite charges. Due to the electromagnetic influence, they can partially and temporarily separate from each other [1, 2, 43, 102]. This procures an oscillation [1, 2, 23, 51]. After the wave has passed, they return to the unperturbed configuration [22, 23, 74, 75, 76]. So, when waves pass through them, IAs’ immaterial leptons manifest themselves as what are known as virtual particles [1, 3]. The Ultimate Equilibrium Equation describes the situation in which the immaterial leptons constituting an IA become real [1, 2]. They are excited by two electromagnetic waves that, from opposite directions, collide

through the same generating IA [1, 2]. This formula is valid only in the transition situation, when the immaterial leptons become real [1, 2].

Figure 1 For the mathematical treatment, in line with the oscillator model, we have considered the charge to be concentrated in a single point [1, 61, 140, 141]. Graphically, this is represented by the black balls in the figures [1]. In reality, the electric charge is probabilistically distributed within an ellipsoidal region of variable dimensions [1]. Following the red line along the y-axis, it can be noted that IA bosons are characterized by alternating spins $s=+1\hbar$ and $s=-1\hbar$. The magnetic component tends to separate the two leptonic charges. After the wave has passed, they return to the unperturbed configuration [22, 23, 74, 75, 76]. This causes the oscillation of the IA boson [1].

In this article we will derive the fundamental laws of IAs, both by a quantum and a classical description. Let's summarize and specify some concepts.

- It seems legitimate to consider the Ultimate Equilibrium, which is due to high energy photons collision [77, 78], as a relativistic excited state [51, 123, 131, 132]. In this situation, special relativity can be therefore approximately respected [10, 15, 16].
- Under certain physical conditions - including relativistic excited states – virtual (immaterial) particles can give rise to observable real states [1, 15, 16, 43, 107, 111] or are in a close relation with them [108, 109, 110, 112].
- We define the following equilibrium situations:
 - Stable, unperturbed equilibrium [1]. Hypothetical condition. In the spacetime of the considered region, i.e. in the considered region of Immaterial Fluid, there are no gravitational or electromagnetic fields, there is no background radiation, there is no form of quantum fluctuations.
 - Quasi-static equilibrium [84, 85, 86]. Physical motivated abstraction. In the spacetime of the considered region, i.e. in the considered region of Immaterial Fluid, there is a weakly curvature, there are no electromagnetic fields or forms of

coherent electromagnetic waves. The quantum fluctuations are present but subdominant.

- Ultimate equilibrium [fig. 2]. The condition from which the two leptonic charges constituting an IA either become real (charge “collapse” [1], from immaterial to real) or return back to the IA state (annihilation, from real to immaterial) [1, 2].
 - With charge “collapse” is to intend kind of densification of the electric charge of the immaterial leptons constituting the IA [1]. It happens with the unmasking of the charges [1]. The charge densification is related to the emergence of the mass of the particle [1]. Other studies present conceptual analogies with that [123, 124, 125, 126, 127].
 - The annihilation process will be explored further in subsequent works. Starting from the considerations presented in Ref. 1, 4, it becomes possible to provide a consistent explanation for the annihilation products observed at different energy scales [15, 23].
 - Two adjacent IAs represent the minimum cell to accommodate a wave in its length [1]. This cell presents null fields and spin $s=0\hbar$ [1, 2].
 - Let’s consider the spacetime as the three-dimensional network made up of IAs [1]. That is, the spacetime is defined by the Immaterial Fluid itself [1]. For what stated so far, the Immaterial Fluid in a stable, unperturbed equilibrium is characterized by overall null fields [1, 2, 3]. From its excitation, mass emerges [1, 2]. Its field is a complex scalar with total spin $s=0$ [1, 2]. Each IA has an internal energy E_{int} due to the attraction between its immaterial leptons [1, 2] (Note B).
 - The transmission of the wave would be the transmission of polarization from an IA to the adjacent one and so on [1, 3]. This interpretation seems to have affinity with other theories concerning the vacuum as a polarizable medium [42, 43], with theories concerning a geometricized electrodynamics [44, 45], with theories of a structured vacuum and discrete spacetime [46].
 - Virtual particles that carry the waves, would be due to the temporary distancing of the leptons constituting the IAs during the oscillation for the transmission of the polarization between the IAs, i.e. for the transmission of the wave [1]. The polarization and the oscillation are transmitted from an IA to the adjacent one and so on [1, 3]. By definition, the delay time is due to the speed of light [1]. The propagation of the wave involves a coherent oscillation of the field [71].
 - The overlapping of IAs charges is to be understood as probabilistically distributed within a region of variable volume [1]. The energy state of the IA affects its size [1, 3]. In particular, during the oscillation, the absorption of energy by the IA causes its

contraction [1, 14, 15, 16, 17]. Under the right conditions, the pair production occurs by permanently concentrating an amount of energy $E=0.511\text{MeV}$ in each lepton constituting the IA [1, 2].

- The charge of each immaterial lepton constituting the IA can theoretically be considered variable with variable density [1, 41]. Once the leptons become real, their charges assume the fixed value of that of electron and positron [1].
- According several theories, real electrons and positrons have an internal structure and are not punctiform [97, 98, 99, 100]. IAs' leptons model, and the real leptons arising from them, could be coherent with such theories [1].
- Before the ultimate equilibrium, the (overall zero) charge distribution of the boson is mathematically assumed to be ellipsoidal [1]. In order to simplify the description of the physical behavior of the IAs, we use an "equivalent bosonic circumference", which is endowed with an "equivalent rotation" around its own spin axis, on the plane perpendicular to it [1]. It is only a geometrical abstraction (Note C).
- Let's consider the transmission of the wave as the transmission of IAs polarization from an IA to the adjacent one and so on [1]. Due to the resulting IA oscillation [1], the peripheral speed of transmission of the polarization, $v=c$, will actually have a "bosonic" circular component and a "fermionic" translational one [1]. As the energy possessed by IA boson increases, its volume decreases [1]. We can introduce the concept of "equivalent rotation" [1] of the IA boson. We define X as the characteristic radial dimension of the boson, which would be mathematically representative of the distribution of its charge [1]. The equivalent rotation of the IA boson is the theoretical rotation of the equivalent bosonic circumference around its spin axis, with its angular speed ω , with its peripheral speed $c = \omega * X$ equal to the light speed and with a period t equal to the time the wave in all its length needs to be transmitted through it [1, 3]. We introduced these quantities to mathematically simplify the work, but they are only a theoretical equivalent reference [1]. In reality, the unmasking of IA leptons occurs in directions conditioned by electric and magnetic fields, based on a complex combination [1] (Note C). Their specific mathematical treatment will be the subject of further investigation.
- Together with the equivalent bosonic circumference, we also introduce the "equivalent IA pair circumference", which has double values of the same physical quantities. For both, in the calculations, we will consider their characteristic dimension X [1].
- We introduced the concept of "equivalent leptonic sphere" [1]. It hypothetically represents a real or immaterial lepton modeled as a spherical surface charge

distribution. It is only a geometrical abstraction that we used to simplify the description of the physical behavior of the real or immaterial lepton [1] (Note C).

- The presented dynamics [1, 2, 3], characterizing the behavior of IAs, that is of the physical vacuum, can be understood as having an efficiency equal to 1 or almost equal to 1 [15, 16, 18, 19].
- We have introduced the concept of “virtual work” of separation W_{virt} of the two IA’s leptonic charges [1, 2]. It is due to the electromagnetic action received by the IA from the wave. It implies a variation of kinetic energy possessed by the forming immaterial masses [2, 23, 43, 102]. These forming masses, still partially overlapping, are distinguishing each other and moving away from each other [1, 2, 43, 102]. The work of separation is associated with a state of oscillation [1, 2, 23, 43, 51]. When the oscillatory excitation due to the perturbation ceases, the internal energy E_{int} due to the electric charges and magnetic dipoles of the immaterial leptons tends to perform the reverse work [23] and restore the situation [43, 51] of stable, unperturbed equilibrium [1, 2] (Note D).

Results

- **Fundamental Equations of the Immaterial Atoms**

- 1) Stable, unperturbed equilibrium. Immaterial state. Bosonic Physics

Due, at the very least, to the background radiation or Higgs field fluctuations, the condition of stable, unperturbed equilibrium is purely theoretical [1]. It is been assumed that IAs distortion is the distortion of spacetime coordinates [1]. Coherent with relativity, the energetic and dimensional state of IAs will be conditioned mostly by the presence of gravitational fields [1, 31, 32, 33]. In the hypothetical condition of stable, unperturbed equilibrium, all IAs, among themselves, will have the same equilibrium value of the physical quantities that characterize them. That is, in the hypothetical absence of gravitational and electromagnetic fields, every point in spacetime is physically equivalent to every other [31, 32, 33, 34]. In the further hypothetical absence of any kind of fluctuations, including Higgs field fluctuations, it means that the variables characterizing IAs would all tend to a common value [1, 2, 35, 36]. In the ideal, stable, unperturbed equilibrium, these variables will be:

E_0 = energy possessed by the IA [1]

t_0 = equivalent rotation period of the IA [1]

p_0 = IA's momentum [1]; as each IA, within certain energy limits, occupies a discrete position in the network, for the calculations its momentum can be associated with its equivalent rotation [1, 133, 134, 135, 136, 137]

X_0 = characteristic dimension of the IA [1].

In the general case, compared with the stable, unperturbed equilibrium condition, the value of the IA's variables may show positive or negative variations [1, 3], summarized by $E = E_0 \pm \Delta E$, $t = t_0 \pm \Delta t$, $p = p_0 \pm \Delta p$, $X = X_0 \pm \Delta X$.

Considering only scalar quantities, we will call Di Massa's laws, the two fundamental laws that describe IAs in the hypothetical condition of stable, unperturbed equilibrium. They have the expression:

$$p_0 * X_0 = \pm \hbar \quad (1)$$

$$E_0 * t_0 = \pm \hbar \quad (2)$$

in which \hbar is the reduced Planck constant. The variable values of the individual IA are halved compared to those of the IA pair [103, 105]. The sign \pm reflects only the quantized direction of the spin. That is, it refers to the alternately opposite orientation of the spin of adjacent IAs [1].

Let's now derive the two laws. The following steps may be further explored or refined. We have defined the field φ as the scalar given by two adjacent IAs, which represent the minimum unit capable of accommodating a wave of unit length [1]. In a similar way to the Klein-Gordon field [15], we have introduced a complex scalar field that represents the quantum configuration of two adjacent IAs, i.e. an IA pair, when they are subjected to the influence of the wave [1]. The wave function satisfies the relativistic wave equation $\square \varphi = \left(\frac{1}{c^2} \partial_t^2 - \partial_x^2 \right) \varphi = 0$ on the condition that $\omega = ck$, where k is the wave number and ω is the angular frequency [1]. This condition implies that the polarization between IAs is transmitted at the speed of light [1], i.e., the transmission of polarization between adjacent IAs is the transmission of the wave [1, 3]. The field of the single pair of IAs becomes formally equivalent to the collective field of the set [79, 95, 96]. The dynamics of the pair of IAs follows that of the mean field, and the phase of the pair coincides with the collective phase [80]. Individual mass is not observable, because there are no spatial or energetic reference points that distinguish it [81]. The only physically significant excitations are the collective modes of the field, which propagate as coherent fluctuations of amplitude and phase [82]. The system can be described by $\varphi(x) = |\varphi(x)|e^{i\theta(x)}$, in which the phase of $\varphi(x)$ can oscillate over time as part of the collective dynamics of the medium [83]. In the absence of dominant incoherent fluctuations, the phase $\theta(t)$ varies periodically over

time. That is, the equivalent bosonic circumference describing the IA pair has a uniform equivalent rotation in the phase. From this we can write $\theta(t) = \omega t$, and so $\varphi(t) = |\varphi|e^{i\omega t}$. This expression also describes the coherent dynamics of the single IA pair, identical to that of the collective field of the set [79, 95, 96]. As in Ref. 1, let us now consider the Lagrangian of the complex scalar field coupled to a gauge field U(1) [15, 20]. So, $\mathcal{L} = -\frac{1}{4} F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu} + |D_\mu\varphi|^2 - V(|\varphi|)$, where $D_\mu = \partial_\mu + ieA_\mu$ is the covariant derivative and $F_{\mu\nu}$ is the electromagnetic tensor. Let's make the field $\varphi(t) = |\varphi|e^{i\omega t}$ explicit in the kinetic term of the Lagrangian, $|D_\mu\varphi|^2$. Let's consider a weakly curved spacetime. Let us now neglect the contributions of the A_μ field, so we do not consider the electromagnetic field. That is, we are in a condition of quasi-static equilibrium [84, 85, 86], with $A_\mu \approx 0$ and $|\varphi(x)|^2 \approx |\varphi|^2$. It implies $D_\mu = \partial_\mu$, therefore the kinetic term becomes $|\partial_\mu\varphi|^2$. Let us consider the energy density associated with the scalar field, $\mathcal{H}_\varphi = |\partial_0\varphi|^2 + |\nabla\varphi|^2 + V(|\varphi|)$. Let us now suppose that the field has an oscillating component of $\varphi(t, \vec{x}) = \rho(\vec{x})e^{-i\omega t}$ type, where $\rho(\vec{x})$ is the spatially distributed modulus of the field and ω is the frequency of the uniform rotation of the phase [87]. This form represents a stationary configuration of the complex scalar field, where the amplitude $\rho(\vec{x})$ is spatially distributed and the temporal dependence corresponds to a uniform rotation of the phase with frequency ω [15, 16, 17, 101], that we can associate with IA pair equivalent rotation. It derives $\frac{\partial\varphi}{\partial t} = -i\omega\varphi$, from which $|\partial_0\varphi|^2 = \omega^2|\varphi|^2$, $|\nabla\varphi|^2 = |\nabla\rho|^2$, and $V(|\varphi|) = V(\rho)$ is obtained. Under the condition of quasi-static equilibrium, we can neglect the spatial contributions of $|\nabla\rho|^2$ and the potential $V(\rho)$ [88, 89, 90]. At this point, we integrate over space and obtain the total energy

$$E = \int d^3x \mathcal{H}_\varphi \approx \int d^3x |\varphi|^2 \omega^2 = \omega^2 \int d^3x |\varphi|^2.$$

As $\omega = 2\pi/t$, then $E = (\frac{2\pi}{t})^2 \int d^3x |\varphi|^2$, from which $E * t = (2\pi)^2/t * \int d^3x |\varphi|^2$. $\int d^3x |\varphi|^2$ can be interpreted as a sort of order parameter that quantifies how extended or concentrated the overall field is [35]. Let us now impose $\int d^3x |\varphi|^2 = 2 * ht/(2\pi)^3$. That is, coherently with what will be discussed in the paragraph Emergence of Time, the extension of the field is proportional to time [2]. This is a normalization of the field, from which, for the IA pair, we obtain $E * t = h/\pi$. In this expression, the indeterminacy regarding the dynamic variables of the field remains [24]. The integral depends on time because the field configuration of the IA pair evolves, i.e. the IA pair contracts, expands or restructures internally [1, 15, 103]. To represent the initial condition where adjacent IAs have alternating spins $s=+1h$ and $s=-1h$, for the individual IA we write $E * t = \pm h/2\pi$. The sign \pm reflects therefore only

the quantized direction of the spin [24, 101]. The variable values of the single IA are halved compared to those of the IA pair [103, 105]. Referring now to the hypothetical condition of stable, unperturbed equilibrium, we can write (2), i.e. $E * t = \pm \hbar \rightarrow E_0 * t_0 = \pm \hbar$. In this expression the variables of all IAs take the same value [15, 17, 103, 104] (Note E).

Let us get now (1), i.e. $p_0 * X_0 = \pm \hbar$. Let's start again from the condition of quasi-static equilibrium. In the context of scalar field fluctuations, the angular momentum is related to the spatial phase of the field φ , so $\varphi(\vec{x}) = \rho(r)e^{in\theta}$, where θ is an angular coordinate and n indicates how many times the phase rotates around the origin [62, 91]. The spatial momentum in the i -th direction is given by $p^i = \int d^3x T^{0i}$. For the complex scalar field $T^{0i} = 2\text{Re}[(D^0 \varphi) * D^i \varphi]$ [15]. IAs occupy discrete position in the network [1]. The momentum of the IA pair will be therefore associated with its equivalent rotation [1, 133, 134, 135, 136, 137]. In a radial and stationary configuration where $\varphi = \rho(r)e^{in\theta}$, $L = n \int d^3x \rho(r)^2$ is obtained, in which L is the orbital angular momentum [65, 91]. Now associating $\varphi(\vec{x}) = \rho(r)e^{in\theta}$ with the equivalent IA pair circumference, the angular momentum will be related to the orbital angular momentum by $p_\theta = \frac{L}{X} = (n/X) \int d^3x \rho(r)^2$, where X is the characteristic dimension [1] of the equivalent IA pair circumference. That is, it is the spatial scale that we make coincide with the characteristic dimension X of the IA pair [1]. Now let's normalize and, by placing $\int d^3x \rho(r)^2 \simeq 1$ [24], we get $p * X \sim n$. With this step we consider the field of the single IA pair as a normalized configuration that represents the typical behavior of all identical IAs present in the homogeneous and coherent medium [65, 91]. To be physically consistent the field must be monovalent, so $\varphi(\theta + 2\pi) = \varphi(\theta)$ [63, 65]. From this, $e^{in2\pi} = 1$ comes, i.e. n must be an integer, that is, the phase is quantized. For the equivalent IA pair circumference with characteristic dimension X , the angular wave function of the theoretical internal rotation is $\psi(\theta) = e^{in\theta}$, with integer n [65, 91]. The angular momentum operator [26] is $L_z = -i\hbar \frac{d}{d\theta}$ [26]. By applying it to the wave function, $L_z \psi(\theta) = -i\hbar \frac{d}{d\theta} e^{in\theta} = \hbar n e^{in\theta}$ is obtained. That is, the orbital angular momentum is quantized [24]. Let us place $\psi(\theta) = 1$ and consider the eigenvalue of the operator [24]. That is, we consider the angular momentum of the single IA pair as representative of the collective [24]. From this, it derives that the associated momentum is [24] $p_\theta = L/X = \hbar n/X$ and so $p_\theta * X = \hbar n$. This is a semiclassical form of the Bohr-Sommerfeld quantization principle, which requires that the action on a closed loop be an integer multiple of \hbar [64, 65]. When $n=2$ we get $p * X = 2\hbar$. This condition corresponds to the lowest non-trivial collective excitation [65, 91] of

the equivalent rotation of the IA pair. Even in this expression, the indeterminacy with respect to the dynamic variables of the field remains. Referring now to the individual IA condition of stable, unperturbed equilibrium, similarly to what was seen for (2), from $p * X = 2\hbar$ we write (1), i.e. $p_0 * X_0 = \pm\hbar$. Also in this case, the variable values are halved compared to those of the IA pair. The sign \pm reflects only the quantized direction of the spin of the individual IAs constituting the pair. That is, it is representative of the arrangement assumed for adjacent IAs [1], having alternately opposite spins $s=+1\hbar$ and $s=-1\hbar$. As already stated, in the hypothetical stable, unperturbed equilibrium the variables of all IAs take the same value (Note E).

Alternatively, let's briefly get the same results by using the relationship between momentum and spatial variation of phase. Still in a quasi-static equilibrium condition, we can write [15, 91] $j^i = ie(\varphi^* \partial^i \varphi - \varphi \partial^i \varphi^*) = \pm 2e|\varphi|^2 \partial^i \theta$. The sign \pm reflects the two possible directions of phase rotation of the field [65]. This corresponds to currents directed in opposite directions, which implies opposite possible orientations of the spin of each IA [1, 65]. In a non-relativistic regime, we assume that no real relativistic motion occurs, but only slow phase rotations [65, 92]. The superflow velocity is proportional to the phase gradient [65, 91], so $\vec{v} = (\frac{\hbar}{m}) \nabla \theta$. Therefore, it turns out $\vec{p} = m\vec{v} = \hbar \nabla \theta$. If the phase $\theta(x)$ associated with the IA pair varies approximately linearly over its characteristic dimension X , its change is $\Delta\theta$, so that $|\nabla\theta| \sim \Delta\theta/X$ [93]. Considering the magnitude of the momentum, we get $p * X = \hbar \Delta\theta$. For a typical phase variation of order $\Delta\theta \approx 2$ we obtain $p * X = 2\hbar$ [65, 66]. From this, as seen above, we get (1) for the individual IA in the hypothetical stable, unperturbed equilibrium.

Now, using a classical approach, we derive the same two laws. As in Ref. 1, we show that with the Immaterial Fluid it is possible to develop both a quantum and a classical mathematical analysis. Let's start from the condition of Ultimate Equilibrium [Fig. 2]. Let's consider the two immaterial leptonic particles an infinitesimal before collapsing and becoming real [1]. They are still partial overlapping and, by definition of IA, they can still convey the wave by their oscillation and internal polarization [1, 3]. From this position they become real, they can separate and manifest themselves in spacetime, or they can return to the condition of IA [1, 2]. In any case, the Zitterbewegung phenomenon [47, 48] can be observed. Coherently to our interpretation, it can be related both to virtual [48] (immaterial) or real [72] particles. At the Ultimate Equilibrium, seen - as stated above - as a relativistic excited state, for each immaterial leptonic particle that is going to collapse [1], we can consider the fundamental equation of special relativity [1, 2, 10, 15]

$$E_*^2 = m^2 c^4 + p_*^2 c^2 \quad (3)$$

Throughout this discussion, the asterisk subscript indicates the condition of Ultimate Equilibrium. Let us consider the expression of the mass of each immaterial leptonic particle at the Ultimate Equilibrium condition [1]

$$m_e = \frac{K_0 Q_e^2}{c^3} * \nu_* \quad (4)$$

In (4), Q_e is the charge of electron or positron, K_0 is Coulomb constant, c is light speed, $\nu_*=1,0638E+23$ 1/s is the frequency of Ultimate Equilibrium [1, 2, 3] (Note F).

Let us now consider the two incident waves with the ultimate equilibrium frequencies, that lead to the Ultimate Equilibrium condition [1, 2] [Fig. 2]. The energy carried by each wave is $E_*=2h\nu_*$. Through (4), for each immaterial particle (3) can be developed as follows:

$p_*^2 c^2 = h^2 \nu_*^2 - \frac{k_0^2 Q_e^4}{c^6} * \nu_*^2 * c^4$, from which $p_*^2 = \frac{\nu_*^2 h^2}{c^2} * \left[1 - \frac{k_0^2 Q_e^4}{h^2 c^2}\right]$, that we rewrite

like this:
$$p_* = \pm \sqrt{\frac{h^2}{c^2} * \left[1 - \frac{k_0^2 Q_e^4}{h^2 c^2}\right] \frac{\nu_*^2}{\nu_*^2}} \quad (5).$$

Figure 2

Configuration at the Ultimate Equilibrium. Immaterial leptonic charges still partially overlap [1, 2]. Each charge distribution is indeterministic [1]. The Zitterbewegung phenomenon could be explained [1, 2, 47, 48, 72]. From this position, the particles become real and separate, or they return in the IA condition and oscillate [1, 2]. A fundamental role is played by the magnetic dipoles of the particles [1, 2, 23]. The mechanism is comparable to a kind of transition state of the fluid [1, 2, 3, 8, 9].

At the Ultimate Equilibrium, the frequency of the wave coincides with the frequency of oscillation of the immaterial leptons and with the frequency related to their equivalent rotation [1, 2]. An infinitesimal before the collapse [1], let us assume the

characteristic dimension X of the equivalent bosonic circumference as coinciding with the characteristic dimension X of each equivalent leptonic sphere.

We impose [1]
$$\frac{c^2}{v_*^2} = 4\pi^2 R_{el}^2 \quad (6)$$

in which R_{el} is the radius of the equivalent leptonic sphere representative of the single immaterial leptonic particle at the Ultimate Equilibrium condition [1]. R_{el} coincides with the Ultimate Equilibrium distance between the center of the two charges [1] [Fig. 2]. Its peripheral speed equal to the light speed is to intend as the wave transmission through IA's oscillation before the charge collapse [1]. After the collapse, as leptons become real, there is no longer for the wave to be transmitted [1]. We use (6) as a particular case, that can be generalized into

$$\frac{c^2}{v^2} = 4\pi^2 X^2 \quad (7)$$

in which X is the characteristic dimension of the equivalent bosonic circumference, that is mathematically representative of the IA's overall null charge distribution [1]. As stated so far, (7) means that the peripheral speed of the equivalent boson is that of light [1], i.e. that polarization is transmitted at the speed of light [1]. This means that the transmission of IAs' polarization is the electromagnetic wave [1]. (5) can be rewritten [2] as:

$$p_* * R_{el} = \pm \hbar \sqrt{1 - \frac{k_0^2 Q_e^4}{h^2 c^2}} \quad (8)$$

By defining the dimensionless quantity

$$K_{ue} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{k_0^2 Q_e^4}{h^2 c^2}} \quad (9)$$

(8) can be rewritten [2] as

$$p_* * R_{el} = \pm K_{ue} \hbar \quad (10)$$

We call K_{ue} "masking factor" at the Ultimate Equilibrium.

(10) is valid at the Ultimate Equilibrium. Related to the equivalent bosonic sphere [1], we generalize it into

$$p * X = \pm K\hbar \quad (11)$$

$K < K_{ue}$ is the value of the “masking factor” before reaching the Ultimate Equilibrium. Based on the discussion of K , it may be deduced that the charge of each IAs’ lepton could be considered variable. These topics can be further explored in later works. Generalizing (9), its formula is

$$K = \sqrt{1 - \frac{k_0^2 Q_u^4}{h^2 c^2}} \quad (12)$$

In which Q_u represents the portion of immaterial leptons’ charges that is unmasked, i.e. freed from masking. It is $0 < Q_u < Q_e$ and its value is indeterministic [1]. As consequence also K is indeterministic [2]. It results

$Q_u = 0$ at the stable, unperturbed equilibrium, or at quasi-static equilibrium. That is, charges are totally masked each other by their complete overlap

$Q_u = Q_e$ at the Ultimate Equilibrium, in which the transition from immaterial to real state occurs. This quantity should be regarded as a theoretical reference parameter rather than a fixed a priori value. In principle, it may be assumed or omitted, since at the Ultimate Equilibrium condition the indeterminate spatial distribution of the leptonic charges may still allow a non-negligible degree of overlap. This follows from the uncertainty principle and from the fluctuating, non-trivial structure of the quantum vacuum [16, 17, 29, 94]. In this sense, the Zitterbewegung phenomenon - related both to virtual (immaterial) or real particles - can be justified [1, 2, 47, 48, 72].

Imposing $R_{el} \neq 0$ we can divide (9) within the root by R_{el}^4 as it follows [2]

$$K_{ue} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{k_0^2 Q_e^4 / R_{el}^4}{h^2 c^2 / R_{el}^4}}$$

from $F_*^2 = k_0^2 Q_e^4 / R_{el}^4$, in which F_* is the electric force between the immaterial charges at the ultimate equilibrium [1], and from (6) we get

$$K_{ue} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{F_*^2}{4\pi^2 \left(\frac{E_*}{R_{el}}\right)^2}} \quad (13)$$

(13) is also writable as

$$K_{ue} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{F_*^2 R_{el}^2}{4\pi^2 E_*^2}} \quad (14)$$

From the consideration that R_{el} is also equal to the Ultimate Equilibrium distance [1], the amount $F_* R_{el}$ can be representative of the “virtual work” [1, 2] W_{*virt} done by the wave to separate [51, 106] the centres of the two immaterial charges, from the initial null distance of total masking up to the distance of Ultimate Equilibrium [1, 2]. This distance, as written above, also coincides with the radius of the electric charge distribution of the particle [1].

We can therefore write $W_{*virt}^2 = F_*^2 R_{el}^2$, from which [2]

$$K_{ue} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{W_{*virt}^2}{4\pi^2 E_*^2}} \quad (15)$$

F_* , as explained above, remains indeterminable [1, 2].

From (11) and (15), let us analyze the particular case of stable, unperturbed equilibrium. The following conclusions, in compliance with the initial hypotheses, are made possible thanks to (4) [1, 2]. Formula (10) is obtained starting from the relativistic excited state of the immaterial particles [51, 123, 131, 132], and considering (3) and (4). At the Ultimate Equilibrium, the transformation of the IAs’ leptons from immaterial to real happens [1]. In the situation of stable, unperturbed equilibrium, the total amount of action [1] of the IA is \hbar . During the oscillation, the two forming, potential leptonic masses partially distinguish each other [1, 2]. So, before reaching the Ultimate Equilibrium, the action takes in account both the bosonic and fermionic contributions [1]. Their total amount is always \hbar [1, 15, 16, 74]. Formula (10), which is indeterministic, admits a standard interpretation when applied to a single fermionic particle: p denotes the momentum operator associated with the particle’s dynamical state, while X represents its position operator in spacetime. If we now consider the bosonic contribution to the action of the IA, as IAs occupy discrete position in the network [1], the quantity expressed in (11) cannot be assigned the same physical interpretation as in (10). (10) is indeed related to the fermionic case at the Ultimate Equilibrium [1]. In the case in which we instead consider the bosonic contribution of the IA action, and so (11), p will represent the momentum associated with the equivalent rotation of the bosonic component of the IA [1, 133, 134, 135, 136, 137], and X will represent the characteristic dimension of the bosonic component of the IA [1].

(14) is obtained in conditions of Ultimate Equilibrium, and it is indeterministic. K_{ue} is a dimensionless, variable quantity. In the case in which the two immaterial charges

are in the stable, unperturbed equilibrium, or if they are in the quasi-static equilibrium (when no coherent waves transit through them), since the work W_{virt} of charges separation is zero [1, 2], from (15) it is obtained

$$K_{\text{ue}} = K = 1 \quad (16).$$

Applying to (11) it follows [2]

$$p * X = \pm \hbar \quad (17)$$

The alternated spin sign $s = \pm 1\hbar$ is in agreement with the immaterial bosons IAs arrangement assumed at the beginning. That is, adjacent IAs, among them, have alternated spin [1] $s=+1\hbar$ and $s=-1\hbar$ [Fig. 2]. In this condition, the action possessed by the boson, quantifiable as \hbar , is such that its momentum can be represented by a stationary rotating charge distribution [1].

For the boson in stable, unperturbed equilibrium we write (17) as follows [2]

$$p_0 * X_0 = \pm \hbar \quad (1)$$

Re-written in the other two conjugated variables [29, 94], E =energy and t =time, (11)

Becomes [2]
$$E * t = \pm K\hbar \quad (18)$$

and (1) becomes [2]

$$E_0 * t_0 = \pm \hbar \quad (2).$$

For each IA immaterial boson, respecting the value \hbar of its spin, the value of the variables E, p, X, t will tend to their respective equilibrium value E_0, p_0, X_0, t_0 that appears in (1) and (2). Compared with the stable, unperturbed equilibrium condition, the value of these quantities may show positive or negative variations, summarized by $E = E_0 \pm \Delta E, t = t_0 \pm \Delta t, p = p_0 \pm \Delta p, X = X_0 \pm \Delta X$ (19). So, considering the equivalent bosonic circumference, we could state that in the hypothetical absence of any kind of perturbation, including any kind of quantum fluctuation, the equations that would describe the behavior of IAs would be (1) and (2).

In the case of quasi-static equilibrium, in which gravitational fields, electromagnetic fields, and coherent electromagnetic waves are absent, IAs do not oscillate as has been described so far. Due to the quantum fluctuations present, from (1) and (2) the equations describing the behavior of IAs become

$$p * X = \pm \hbar \quad (17) \quad \text{and} \quad E * t = \pm \hbar \quad (20).$$

The value of the variables E, t, p, X - given by (19) - is indeterministic. If p increases, X has to decrease, and vice versa. The same happens for E and t [1, 15, 16].

When $K = 1$ the IA boson is therefore in a quasi-static equilibrium or in the stable, unperturbed equilibrium condition, in which X can assume very large values, hypothetically even thousands of km [1]. In this situation, from (12) derives that $Q_u = 0$. It coherently means that in this situation the electric charge of the immaterial lepton is totally masked by the other. That is, the quantum of action \hbar , with dimension [J*s], is totally possessed by the boson [1].

2) Wave propagation. Immaterial state. Bosonic and fermionic physics

Values $0 < K < 1$ identify the immaterial condition, in which virtual (immaterial) particles indirectly manifest themselves as electromagnetic waves transit through IAs [1]. Gravitational waves, within certain limits, do not induce electromagnetic phenomena or the appearance of virtual particles [31, 37, 38, 39, 40]. For what stated so far, virtual particles arise by IAs oscillation due to the propagation of the wave. One or more waves freely propagate through the transmission of the polarization of the IA bosons [1]. By definition, in the portion of IA boson directly polarized by the wave, the polarization is transmitted at the speed c of the electromagnetic wave [1]. On the remaining portion we cannot say anything deterministic [1]. When K tends from 1 to 0, decreases the action possessed by the immaterial boson and increases the action of the individual, forming immaterial leptons that are unmasking [1, 15, 16, 74]. The total amount is always \hbar [1, 15, 16, 74]. The momentum less depends on the equivalent rotation of the boson and more on the motion of the leptonic charges, which are more and more distancing and distinguishing as the oscillation amplitude increase [1] (Note G). (11) and (18) consider the equivalent rotation of the boson and not the motion of the fermionic particles that are developing. The bosonic equivalent rotation describes the behaviour of the IA boson, not of the immaterial or real leptons, i.e. fermions. The value of K tells us how much the action \hbar acts in a bosonic or a fermionic way. This is a purely qualitative consideration. Indeed, as already mentioned, both K and the dynamical variables are indeterministic.

3) Ultimate Equilibrium. Transition state from immaterial to real

$K=0$. Ends the bosonic physics and begins the fermionic one [Fig. 2]. The two leptons have mass $E_m = \frac{K_0 Q_e^2}{c} * v_* = 0,511 \text{MeV}$ [1, 2]. In this condition, it can be considered that the transition from immaterial to real state occurs, even if the particles still remain partially overlapping [1, 2]. The partial overlap of both virtual (immaterial) or real leptons could give rise to kind of a Zitterbewegung phenomenon related to pairs generation [1, 2, 47, 48, 72].

4) Real particles state. Fermionic physics

If separation occurs, each particle moves away [1, 2] according to $E^2 = m^2 c^4 + p^2 c^2$. Their generation gives rise to the gravitational field [1, 2]. The action is entirely fermionic (Note C). The particles that are born could be considered to be in a state of Entanglement [51, 52, 53]. In a subsequent work, starting from the physical vacuum conceived as an Immaterial Fluid medium made up of Immaterial Atoms, we will provide a physical, clear explanation for a basic interpretation of the Entanglement.

- **Emergence of time**

For simplicity's sake, let's consider only the equivalent bosonic circumference. As already mentioned, it is mathematically representative of the behavior of the IA [1, 3] (Note C). We will therefore use only formulas (17) and (20), taking into account the possible variations of the values of the variables according to the expressions (19), i.e. $E = E_0 \pm \Delta E$, $t = t_0 \pm \Delta t$, $p = p_0 \pm \Delta p$, $X = X_0 \pm \Delta X$. Further developments will be possible in future works. For the moment, we emphasize the conceptual foundations of the theory.

The equivalent rotation period t [1] represents the unit of time and indicates how fast time flows. According to (20) it depends on the energy possessed by the IA [1]. It is also related to the oscillation of the two immaterial charged leptons that make up the IA [1]. The frequency of the wave coincides with the oscillation frequency of the two immaterial leptons [1]. In the hypothetical situation of stable, unperturbed equilibrium all IAs have the same characteristic dimension X_0 , same equivalent rotation period t_0 , same energy E_0 and momentum p_0 [1]. The set of IAs constituting spacetime [1] remains in the same state, which could be considered a stationary state. This means that there are no dynamic evolutions that could show the flow of time. There would not be time perception [46, 118, 119, 120]. When in a region of the spacetime a variation of the IAs energy state occurs, it also implies their t variation according to (20). By this difference we have the perception of time, because in this subsystem IAs are characterized by different values of the observables [54, 120, 121]. This difference represents a dynamic evolution with respect to the initial global system. This basic interpretation could be coherent with the Page and Wootters approach, that describe time as an emergent property of a quantum system, rather than as an external absolute parameter [54, 55, 56, 57, 58, 59].

All bodies are in motion, even planets or other bodies with strong gravity, such as black holes. Considering the vacuum as the Immaterial Fluid medium, they are in motion in relation to the Immaterial Fluid. In Ref. 1 and 2, in analogy with other theories [113, 114, 115, 116, 117], we described the arise of the gravitational field as

an emergent property of the Immaterial Fluid. When the elementary particle occupies different positions, with its passage it dilates new involved IAs according to (17) [1]. This implies that, according to (20), the dilated IAs will have a greater equivalent rotation period than the others. As discussed above, this means that time flows more slowly in the vicinity of the particle, i.e. in the vicinity of the mass.

Extending this concept to big masses, consisting of a large number of real particles, such as a planet, IAs dilated by the passage of the planet would be in large quantities. Due to the motion of the planet at every instant there would be new IAs dilated by the passage of the mass. With the same reasoning exposed for the real particle, around the planet, which is in motion with respect to the Immaterial Fluid, there are always dilated IAs. Still according to (17) and (20), this implies that around a large mass there would always be dilated IAs and therefore always IAs with a larger equivalent rotation period. Within certain limits, the greater the mass of the planet, the more IAs will be dilated. Their equivalent rotation period will also be greater. This means that time flows proportionally more slowly in the vicinity of a large mass, in accordance with what is predicted by relativity.

- **Invariance of light speed**

Using spacetime as a three-dimensional network of IAs, by means the wave trajectory, we have already derived the invariance of the speed of light [1]. The summary of the procedure is reported in the paragraph “Fundamental Equations of the Immaterial Atoms” in this article. We have derived the invariance of light speed also through a classical analysis, considering the equivalent bosonic circumference [1]. By definition of equivalent bosonic circumference is $c = \omega_{eq} * X$ (21), where ω_{eq} is its angular speed, X its characteristic dimension [1]. Based on the hypothesis of polarization transmission along the equivalent circumference [1], from (21) we can write $c = 2\pi\nu_0 * X$. Then, considering the wave length $\lambda_0 = 1/\nu_0$, if we impose that $X = \lambda_0/2\pi$, we easily get [1] the fundamental relation for electromagnetic waves in vacuum $c = \lambda_0\nu_0 = \lambda\nu$. Saying that the bosonic circumference has a characteristic dimension $X = \lambda_0/2\pi$, where λ_0 is the length of the wave acting on the IA, is to say that the equivalent bosonic circumference is exactly as long as the wavelength on the Cartesian plane [1]. This passage is coherent with formula (7) of the present article. (7) is been used to obtain IAs fundamental laws.

Now let us derive the invariance of light speed, but using a further procedure. Through this procedure, we are going to explain the physical phenomenon that determines the invariance. Let us consider, as already stated, the transmission of the wave as the transmission of the polarization between one IA and the adjacent one and so on [1].

As for the emergence of time, for simplicity's sake we only consider the equivalent bosonic circumference. From (17), (20), (19), and $c=E/p$, that is valid for photons, it follows that

$$c=X/t \quad (22)$$

in which boson's characteristic dimension X depends on the energy or momentum possessed by the boson according to (17) and (20), and boson equivalent rotation period t remains automatically conditioned [1]. (22) defines light speed as the characteristic dimension and the equivalent rotation period of the IA vary, depending on the energy it possesses. In this case energy is conditioned by the passage of the polarizing electromagnetic wave [1]. The variations of characteristic dimension and equivalent rotation period will be in such a ratio as to always guarantee the same value c of the wave propagation speed. (22) is in agreement with $p=h/\lambda$, in which, as the momentum of the photon increases, a shorter wavelength corresponds [122]. This, based on (17) and (20), leads to a smaller characteristic dimension X and a smaller equivalent rotation period t , so that through (22) light speed remains constant. The same result occurs if the momentum of the photon decreases.

- **Invariance of interference in Michelson-Morley experiment**

Michelson-Morley experiment [67] led to conclude the aether as not existent. In reality, considering the vacuum as the Immaterial Fluid medium made up of IA bosons, with alternated spin $s=\pm 1\hbar$, the condition that the speed of the light must be constant still remains respected [1]. Indeed, according to (22), regardless of the reference system, the speed of light depends on the ratio between the dimensions of the IAs the electromagnetic wave transits through and their equivalent rotation period t . The value of these variables, as described above, depends on the momentum and energy possessed by the IAs owing to the electromagnetic wave transmitted through them [1, 2]. In relation to the experiment, in the forward propagation of the light parallel to the "aether wind" [67] it is assumed, for example, that the "aether wind" entails a hypothetical decrease in speed. In this case the photons have a lower momentum than they would in the absence of the "aether wind" [67]. According to (17), (20) and (22), the energy possessed by the IA boson is also lower, hence the increase of X and t in such a way that, as discussed above, their ratio $c=X/t$ remains constant. Conversely, it happens in the case when the light propagates with "aether wind" in favour [67], that is X and t decrease in such a way that their ratio still remains constant and equal to c . It is possible to make similar reasoning also for beams perpendicular to the "aether wind". Considering the vacuum as made up of IAs, through (17) and (20) what varies between beams traveling in different directions with respect to the "aether wind" is the frequency. By rotating the device, photon beams that propagate

through IAs change frequency between them, but they always travel at the same speed $c=X/t$. Moreover, in the last path before reaching the detector, beams travel parallel to each other [67], so they have same momentum and therefore same frequency. Even in intermediate configurations, with photon beams that propagate in oblique directions with respect to the "aether wind", the trajectories can be decomposed in parallel and perpendicular directions to it (Note H).

Conclusions

In this article, starting from the physical vacuum conceived as Immaterial Fluid, we have confirmed -as in the preparatory work [1] - that it is possible to develop a description with quantum and covariant mathematics, but also a coherent description with classical mathematics [1]. In particular, we have derived the laws that describe the behavior of its constituent elements, the Immaterial Atoms. We have physically described time as an emergent property of the superfluid medium. We have demonstrated in several ways how the speed of light remains constant through the Immaterial Fluid, providing a clear physical explanation of the phenomenon. In this way, from the point of view of the physical behavior, we have clarified why no variation in interference is observed in the Michelson-Morley experiment. Starting from a model of spacetime conceived as Immaterial Fluid, it is possible to propose a unified description of different phenomena that, in the conventional treatment, appear conceptually disjointed or do not present a defined framework. Experimental observations that lack a clear and intuitive explanation thus acquire not only a coherent mathematical formulation, but also a possible more direct physical interpretation, more closely aligned with our intuition of natural phenomena.

Notes

A Particles possessing intrinsic spin and electric charges have a magnetic dipole moment proportional to their spin, and therefore behave as magnetic dipoles [23, 24]. In this article, we will use the notion of magnetic dipoles of charged leptons to develop the description of the process.

B Higgs field is a scalar, has nonzero VEV, and it undergoes quantum fluctuations [10, 11]. From our perspective, as an indication, it could be reasonable to consider the following reasoning. Let us assume the Higgs field as emergent from the field associated to a set of pairs or multiples of pairs of adjacent IAs. Its VEV could be related to the internal energy E_{int} associated to the corresponding IAs [1, 2]. Higgs boson is the energy associated with a local oscillation of the Higgs field that propagates through the spacetime [68, 69, 142]. As a first approximation, in analogy with certain studies that hypothesize the Higgs boson as composed of other particles [12, 13], we could consider it as due by

the energy associated with the oscillation of a proper number of pairs of adjacent IAs [1]. Similarly, for example, we might consider developing a theory that would associate the electron field with the field due to the set of all IAs immaterial leptons, each of them considered as separate from the others. Based on Ref. 4, the quark fields would be associated with fields related to suitable combinations of immaterial leptons. The electromagnetic field, with the field relative to the set of single IAs, each considered separate from the others. In general, one might consider developing a theory that associates all fundamental fields with the fields relative to suitable combinations of immaterial leptons. So, a theory in which all fields can be traced back to the presence of the immaterial leptons constituting the IAs. These topics will be explored further in subsequent works.

C The “diametrical circumference of the equivalent bosonic sphere”, hereafter simply referred to “equivalent bosonic circumference”, and the “equivalent leptonic sphere” are geometrical abstractions that we used to simplify the description respectively of the physical behavior of the IAs and of the leptons [1]. They cannot be considered realistic [1]. For both, in the calculations, we will consider their characteristic dimension X , which in the general case will coincide with their radius [1]. The equivalent bosonic circumference represents the IA boson [1]. Each “equivalent leptonic sphere” hypothetically represents both an immaterial or a real lepton modeled as a spherical surface charge distribution [1]. Its theoretical rotation is constructed to reproduce the same physical effects as those attributed to the real lepton. The primary effect considered is the intrinsic angular momentum, i.e. the spin. Although spin is not the result of spatial rotation in quantum theory [16, 24], the model is constructed to formally recover its observable effects [1]. The initial spin/angular momentum of the IA boson is conserved. Once the charge collapse [1] has occurred and the real charges separate [1], it is redistributed between the intrinsic spins of the fermions and their relative orbital angular momentum [1, 49, 50].

IA’s oscillation due to the electromagnetic effect of the wave, in reality involves a complex distortion [1]. Starting from the hypothetical condition of stable, unperturbed equilibrium, the oscillation implies a deformation of the IA [1]. This deformation is characterized by a decrease in the bosonic component, with radial contraction and relative displacement of the charges, and an expansion of the forming, immaterial fermionic component of the charges in a direction parallel to the spin [1]. The global, resulting distortion of the IA will be due by the combination of the two components [1]. If the incident waves have low energies, the characteristic dimension X of the boson is theoretically much greater than the distance between the forming leptonic charges [1].

To further show the coherence of this model [1], adopting the same, unrealistic hypothesis for the historical calculation of electron’s classic radius $r_e = 2,818 * 10^{-15}m$ [1, 22, 23], we obtained the same identical value of the radius, but through a different procedure [1]. We then demonstrated how, assuming instead an internal structure of the electron (and positron) and an internal distribution of electric charge [97, 98, 99, 100], one can actually justify any possible experimental value of the electron radius [1].

D The concept of “virtual work” of charges separation [1, 2] could be used to explain one of the ways in which the apparent violation of energy conservation occurs in virtual (immaterial) particle processes [10, 15, 16, 19, 20]. If the electromagnetic wave is polarized perpendicular to the spin axis, that is, if the magnetic force that tends to separate the two charges is directed parallel to the spin axis of the IA, then all the disturbing magnetic energy will become “virtual work” according to the

dynamics already described [1]. It will involve the movement of the immaterial forming masses [1] while respecting the conservation of energy. This scenario is coherent with a Lagrangian description of the interaction, where the work done by the acting forces is balanced by the variation in the potential energy of the system [15, 16, 19, 21]. If the force of the magnetic field is not parallel to the spin axis, a quantity of energy will be dispersed in a direction perpendicular to the spin axis. This results in two torques with zero resultant [22, 23, 24, 25]. The component of the magnetic force directed parallel to the spin axis will lead to a distancing of two immaterial forming masses [1, 2, 22, 23, 26, 27, 28], but there is overall no observable conservative energy balance, leading to a description in which energy conservation appears to be locally violated [15, 20]. Energy balance is respected if we insert the contributions relating to the “virtual work” W_{virt} of separation of the forming leptonic charges and the related kinetic terms [1, 2]. These quantities arise as a consequence of the influence of the electromagnetic wave [1, 2]. More generally, temporary violation also occurs through energy fluctuations [15, 24, 25, 29] transmitted through IAs.

E Unlike uncertainty inequalities, (1) and (2) represent deterministic constraints between physical quantities, expressing quantization conditions. Hypothetically, in a stable, unperturbed equilibrium, i.e. in the absence of any form of radiation, quantum fluctuations, gravitational fields, and in the absence of any Higgs field fluctuation, there would not exist non-commuting operators [16, 46]. The uncertainty would not have an applicable physical content. From what stated so far, we can theoretically assume that uncertainty, both from a physical and mathematical point of view, would arise when IAs are not in the hypothetical state of stable, unperturbed equilibrium. That is, in reality, uncertainty is always present everywhere in spacetime [29].

F The relation $m_e = \frac{K_0 Q_e^2}{c^3} * \nu_*$ is been obtained in ref.1. It links electromagnetic parameters to electron’s (or positron) mass. At the Ultimate Equilibrium frequency, which is obtained by dynamic consideration during the oscillation of the IA, it gives exactly the value $m_e = 0,511\text{MeV}$ [1]. In $m_e = \frac{K_0 Q_e^2}{c^3} * \nu_*$, Q_e represents the charge of electron or positron. Based on the described mechanism of emergence of virtual particles and of the gravitational field [1], one could hypothesize to derive a similar, theoretical expression of the virtual (immaterial) particles’ mass. This would be an indeterministic value. It would depend on the frequency of the waves passing through the IAs -in the general case different from ν_* - and from the indeterministic, unmasked portion Q_u of the leptonic electric charges. The value of this immaterial mass would still remain indeterministic.

A series of experiments for the detection of electrons [30] have been conducted in which peaks of pion production have been highlighted in a vicinity of ν_* . We have published a consistent article [4] in which we manage to prove how, theoretically, these pions can be considered as derived from a suitable combination of electrons and positrons [1, 4].

G As the energy increases, the amplitude of the internal oscillation of the IA grows [1]. At the same time, higher energy states correspond to a reduction in the characteristic spatial extension of the IA [1]. This behavior can be interpreted, in analogy with relativistic effects, as an effective contraction of the spacetime coordinates associated with the IA. Consequently, the absolute amplitude of the oscillation, defined over this contracted region, tends to decrease [138, 139].

H An experiment sufficient to demonstrate the existence of the Immaterial Fluid has already been discussed and performed with positive results [1, 60]. It is been quickly published with documentary

value and as a stimulus for further investigations [60]. However, it was not technically possible to exclude with absolute certainty the influence of external factors or possible systematic errors [1]. We therefore expect to repeat it under controlled conditions.

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